

IMPROVING MECHANISMS OF AESTHETIC EDUCATION THROUGH DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE COMPETENCE IN PRESCHOOL TEACHERS

Saidova Feruza Akramovna

Teacher of the Department of "Preschool, Primary and Special Training Methodologies" of the National Center for Teaching Educators to New Methodologies of Surkhandarya Region

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10829179>

Abstract. *According to the requirements of the present day, along with the professional skills, knowledge, intelligence, creativity of the educator, it is necessary to improve the mechanisms of aesthetic education. This article talks about the existing problems in improving aesthetic education and mastering it through the development of creative competence of teachers.*

Keywords: *pedagogue, educator, aesthetics, creativity, competence, pedagogical skill, professional competence, functional tasks of a pedagogue, pedagogical ability, pedagogical technique, pedagogical qualimetry, pedagogical attitude.*

As an important professional quality of the person - the readiness of the educator to implement aesthetic education in a psychological-pedagogical approach includes the unity of the following components:

- motivational - conscious interest in the educational profession, positive attitude to the educator's work, understanding the theoretical problems of aesthetic education and the importance of applying them to the practice of the preschool educational organization;
- orientation-aesthetic and artistic consciousness, knowledge in the field of aesthetic education of children of preschool educational organization;
- evaluator - the ability to perceive, evaluate and interpret aesthetics, a high level of aesthetic needs, feelings, tastes and ideals;
- operative - acquiring the skills and qualifications of aesthetic education, speech culture, aesthetics of appearance and behavior.

Sufficient development and expressiveness of these components, and their unity is an indicator of the high level of professional, psychological-pedagogical preparation of the educator for aesthetic education, that is, the aesthetic culture of the educator has been formed to a certain extent. Their lack of development indicates that educators are not prepared for aesthetic education to a certain extent, and their low level of aesthetic development.

By supporting children in the process of preschool education, it is necessary to create favorable conditions for forming them as subjects of education, striving for self-development and regular improvement. For this, it is required to develop a methodology for organizing educational activities aimed at intellectual development of children through pedagogical support in preschool educational organizations. In turn, there is a need to prepare pedagogic personnel to work on the basis of this methodology. First of all, pedagogues should have good knowledge in order to provide proper education to students. Only then will we be able to train people who are necessary for our society.

Providing aesthetic education in preschool age means forming a foundation for educating a child from a young age. In supporting the intellectual development of children, it is necessary to

rely on their personality and identity. Accordingly, the paradigm of preschool education changes and requires the research of new theory and practice of preschool education. Within the framework of such a theory, helping to realize children's intellectual formations and their potential in this field is an integral component of person-oriented education. We have to admit that the level of formation of aesthetic culture among educators of pre-school education organizations today determines low indicators.

We can determine this from the low views of preschool education. The reason for this is primarily the educators themselves, even though they have been given the status of pedagogues, they do not behave like pedagogues, developing new ideas and methods to achieve effective indicators during children's leisure time. , we can take as an example that they are not working on themselves, but some unnecessary conversations, educators are busy with each other, or they are engaged in unproductive work.

These reasons are closely related to each other, and another reason why they do not behave like pedagogues is that they do not have a complete higher education. Although the first educational direction of the educational stage begins with preschool education, the idea that a child acquires 70% of his knowledge during his life from the kindergarten age, the strong knowledge and level is required from the teacher who forms these high results. We must pay attention to the fact that all of them must have a higher education in order for the educator to achieve a strong level of knowledge and skills.

Educators who do not have higher education are more practical in their work, and theoretically they do not have many skills and knowledge. This, in turn, is the basis for determining their own competence and incomplete formation of aesthetic culture. Today, one of the most urgent problems preventing the formation of aesthetic culture is the fact that teachers are not familiar with fiction and do not read books. Although closeness to literary works encourages everyone to be creative and calls to beauty. While reading the works, the stages of aesthetic education begin to form in the heart of the reader based on such characters as feelings of sympathy, feelings of kindness, feeling good and evil and distinguishing the differences between them. In this case, we can determine that this quality is at a high level among educators with higher education. Because during education, they read many books to find out the necessary information. Educators who do not have higher education can hardly remember the last time they read a book.

It is impossible to imagine that educators do not have spiritual and aesthetic education. But how to find the precious key of children's hearts, how to open the huge reserves of their aesthetic development? There can be only one answer: to study the age and individual characteristics of children. The complexity of organizing and managing the creative process is that not only conscious, but also subconscious concepts of creative individuality appear in it.

A teacher-educator does not become a creator by himself. His creative ability is formed through consistent study and work on himself over a period of time, and it gradually improves and develops. As in the case of any specialist, the foundation is laid in the student years for future pedagogues to have creativity and it is consistently developed in the organization of professional activity. It is important for the pedagogue to direct himself to creative activity and be able to organize this activity effectively.

When organizing creative activities, the teacher should pay special attention to the creation of creative products of a problematic nature. Self-creative activation is not the ability of a person to fully demonstrate and develop his abilities in creative activities, but to organize activities in the

spirit of creativity and creativity, to develop new ideas. it is necessary to try it in the educational process.

Self-creative activation is not the full manifestation and development of one's potential in creative activities, being creative and creative or not, but organizing activities in the spirit of creativity, creativity, new ideas it is necessary to strive to try in the educational process. In the activities, "creativity moves in the following 4 directions according to the road map, and the actions in them are the signs that express the creativity of pedagogues:

- 1) demonstration of creative thinking skills;
- 2) to be able to use strategies that encourage learning with interest;
- 3) innovative approach and creative approach to finding solutions to pedagogical issues;
- 4) expected result.

We mentioned above that the aesthetic culture of the educator is manifested in his thinking, communication, and feelings in certain types of activities. Aesthetic culture based on creativity to advance a problem or scientific hypothesis; hypothesis testing and modification; identifying the problem based on changing the results of the decision; it expresses sensitivity to the mutual opposition of knowledge and practical actions in finding a solution to a problem. The pedagogue's ability to acquire the qualities of aesthetic education through the development of creative competence directs his personal abilities, natural and social strength, professional activity to quality and efficient organization.

Creativity and aesthetic culture are contagious; in order to have a creative or aesthetic culture, a person should communicate with more creative people or people with high aesthetic culture and always be in search. As it is possible to develop any skill, it is possible to develop the ability of creative thinking or the ability to have an aesthetic culture. It helps future pedagogues to think in an unusual way, not only after becoming an educator, but also from the time of future education. However, encouraging future pedagogues to be creative and developing aesthetic culture depends on how qualified the teacher is.

Forming an aesthetic attitude to reality in pedagogues gives them the opportunity to develop a high artistic and aesthetic taste, to know the original beauty of social aesthetic ideals. The topics of the natural-mathematical cycle help to reveal the beauty of nature in children, to form a desire to protect and preserve it. The subjects of the humanitarian cycle show an aesthetic picture of human relationships. The artistic-aesthetic cycle introduces children to the world of magical art. Objects of the utilitarian-practical cycle allow to penetrate the secrets of the beauty of labor, the human body, teach the skills of creating, maintaining and developing beauty. It is important for the teacher to confirm the beauty of mental work, business relations, knowledge, mutual assistance, joint activity.

Artistic abilities in the field of drawing, modeling, singing, expressive reading are stabilized. Thanks to practical exercises, artistic perception is thinner and more differentiated. The fact that the child checks the correctness of the line drawn in his practice, the shade of color in the decorative image, the correctness of the intonation of the song, the expressiveness of the intonations expressing question, surprise, joy, fear makes him listen and look closer. Perception enriched with new impressions, in turn, encourages the child to more confident and voluntary actions.

Artistic abilities are also more clearly manifested in individual children: observation (a sense of color and shape when drawing), a melodic ear (singing simple songs independently

clearly), a sense of rhythm (placing patterns in a decorative pattern, clearly, rhythmically). Naturally, this is done only on the condition that children are constantly led to perform various tasks: distinguishing tone relationships, comparing shapes, colors, lines, etc., determine a high level of formation in children.

REFERENCES

1. Abdullayeva, V. (2023). MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM YOSHIDAGI BOLALARNING DUNYOQARASHINI SHAKLLANTIRISH YO'LLARI. QO 'QON UNIVERSITETI XABARNOMASI, 888-891.
2. Abdullayeva, V. (2023). XIX ASRNING IKKINCHI YARMIDA TURKISTONDA TA'LIM JARAYONNI YUZAGA KELISHI VA DARSLIKLAR. QO 'QON UNIVERSITETI XABARNOMASI, 841-843.
3. Kadirov U. FACTORS AND IMPORTANCE OF FORMING PERSONAL CONSCIOUSNESS IN THE INFORMATION SOCIETY. American Journal of Pedagogical and Educational Research. Volume 18, | November,2023.
4. Umarov B, The Cramming Method Is An Important Tool For Forming Learner Communicative Competence. Historical Experience, International Journal of Academic Management Science Research (IJAMSR), 2021/2, p. 91-94.